

EFFECT OF THE MANUFACTURING PROCESS AND SKIN-CORE ADHESION EFFICIENCY ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF A THERMOPLASTIC SANDWICH

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SUMMARY

In this work the changes in the mechanical properties of a thermoplastic sandwich due to different manufacturing processes and skin-core adhesion efficiency were investigated. For this reason different composite sandwiches with PET foam core and Twintex skins were realized, tested and analyzed with Finite Element Method.

Keywords: thermoplastic sandwich, experimental characterization, interfacial properties, finite element analysis, fracture analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Composite sandwich structures made of both thermoplastic skins and core are finding increasing use in marine and transportation industries. These thermoplastic sandwiches offer many advantages over thermoset panels including recyclability, ease of manufacture, high toughness and reparability. However the design and verify of such structures need to investigate different parameters due to their intrinsic non-homogeneity, including skin and core stiffness and adhesion characteristics [1-4].

The aim of this work was to investigate the changes in the mechanical properties of a thermoplastic sandwich due to different manufacturing processes and to a different skin-core adhesion efficiency. For this reason composite sandwiches with PET foam core and Twintex skins were realized with different manufacturing processes (vacuum bagging and compression moulding). Moreover the possibility of enhancing the skin core adhesion by the mean of a copolymer low temperature melting film was evaluated.

Three and four points flexural tests were performed according to ASTM C393 standard, for a complete static mechanical characterization on the samples obtained from the different realised sandwich. Moreover debond tensile fracture in sandwich beams was experimentally examined, in order to acquire significant comparison parameters.

The mechanical properties of the sandwich beams were also analyzed using the finite element method (nonlinear analysis), determining the load distribution along the skin-core interface length of the laminates.

By analyzing experimental and numerical results it was possible to extend the knowledge of mechanical properties of this kind of thermoplastic sandwich panels, and to find significant indications on the costs-properties relationship.

1. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Fig.1 contains a summary of the three Twintex/PET foam sandwiches examined in this work. In all sandwiches the skins were based on composites containing four layers of a Twintex T PP balanced fabric made of Twintex® rovings (commingled E-glass and polypropylene filaments, areal weight 745 g/m²). The core material was an close-cell PET foam, (the Divinycell P foam provided by DIAB), having a density of 110 kg/m³. Sandwich A was considered to be a standard system in which the skins were consolidated directly on the PET foam with the vacuum bagging process. Consolidation was done by heating above melting temperature of PP matrix (180°C-190°C), and skin-core adhesion is only due to the flow of PP matrix within the foam cells. Sandwich B was realised as the previous one, expect for the introduction of a low melting temperature (LM) adhesive film (BEMIS 5250 polyester based copolymer) with the aim to enhance the skin-core adhesion. Sandwich C was realised by two step compression moulding technique. At first Twintex skins were consolidated by isothermal compression moulding, by heating at 180 °C and applying 10 bar pressure, before cooling step under pressure. In the second step the skins were sealed to the core by heating the film above its melting temperature (165°C) and applying a low pressure (1-2 bar) before cooling step under pressure.

Fig.1 Summary of the sandwiches examined in this study.

1.1 Flexural test

Flexural properties of sandwiches were determined according to ASTM C393 [5] with *midspan loading* and *quarter point loading* configurations. A MTS Insight 100 testing machine equipped with a 10 kN load cell was used, at a crosshead displacement rate of 5 mm/min. In a first step load was applied by means of steel bars, in order to determine sandwich bending stiffness and shear rigidity: this tests were arrested in the elastic region of the stress-strain curve. Then rubber pads were used to distribute the load, and

the sandwich shear strength was determined by applying increasing load up to the core failure.

Flexural stiffness D and core shear modulus G were determined from simultaneous solution of the deflection equations as follows:

$$D = \frac{P_1 L_1^3 [1 - (11L_2^2 / 8L_1^2)]}{48\Delta_1 [1 - (2P_1 L_1 \Delta_2 / P_2 L_2 \Delta_1)]} \quad (1)$$

$$G = \frac{P_1 L_1 c [8L_1^2 / 11L_2^2 - 1]}{\Delta_1 b (d + c)^2 [(16P_1 L_1^3 \Delta_2 / 11P_2 L_2^3 \Delta_1) - 1]} \quad (2)$$

where P_1 / Δ_1 is the slope of the *load-midspan deflection* curve in midspan loading configuration on span L_1 , P_2 / Δ_2 is the slope of the *load-midspan deflection* curve in quarter point loading configuration on span L_2 , c and d are the core and sandwich thickness respectively, b is the sandwich width.

D can be expressed also as follows (same facings sandwich):

$$D = \frac{E(d^3 - c^3)b}{12} \quad (3)$$

Shear strength was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Midspan loading: } \tau = \frac{P_{\max}}{(d + c)b} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Quarter point loading: } \tau = \frac{P_{\max}}{(d + c)b} \quad (5)$$

where P_{\max} is the load applied at core failure.

1.2 Interfacial fracture tests

The skin-core interfacial fracture properties of the three sandwiches were characterised by using the three-point-bend specimen shown in fig.2 [6-7].

Fig.2 Schematic illustration of the interfacial fracture test specimen.

Part of the lower end of the sandwich specimens was removed leaving the upper skin extending at one end, and a pre-crack was introduced. Then the specimen was loaded as shown in Fig. 2, and crack propagation was measured by means of a grid applied to the skin-core region. A MTS Insight 100 testing machine equipped with a 10 kN load cell was used. The specimen was repeatedly loaded and unloaded (at a crosshead displacement rate of 1 mm/min) in order to detect visible crack increases: in the unloading phase the new reduced compliance of the specimen, due to the crack propagation, was calculated.

The interfacial fracture energy was calculated by means of an experimental compliance method [6-7], where the interfacial fracture energy G_C was given by:

$$G_C = \frac{P^2}{2B} \frac{dC}{da} \quad (6)$$

where P is the applied load, B the specimen width, C the specimen compliance and a the crack length. The specimen compliance can be expressed as a function of crack length in the following form:

$$C = C_0 + Ka^3 \quad (7)$$

where C_0 is the initial compliance and K was determined by measuring the slope of the graph obtained by plotting the compliance C against a^3 .

2. FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

2.1 Finite element analysis of flexural test

The shear stress distribution in a flexural test with both midspan and quarter point loading configurations was determined with Ansys 11.0 software. Here a plain strain, two-dimensional, non linear analysis was performed. Contact was modelled with both steel bars and rubber pads, in order to evaluate the changes in shear stress distributions with these different loading configurations. In fig.3 a schematic of analysis main characteristics and adopted mesh is reported [8].

Fig.3 Schematic illustration of FEM analysis main characteristics (flexural tests).

2.2 Finite element analysis of the interfacial fracture tests

The loading conditions at the crack tip were determined by carrying out a finite element analysis of the three-point-bend specimen geometry with Ansys 11.0 software. The analysis was plane strain, two-dimensional, non linear. Fracture along skin-core interface was modelled by means of cohesive zone model [9]: the interface was represented by a special set of interface or contact elements, and a bilinear cohesive zone model was used to characterize the constitutive behaviour of the interface. In fig.4 an image of analysis main characteristics and adopted mesh is reported.

Fig.4 Schematic illustration of FEM analysis main characteristics (interfacial fracture tests).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Flexural tests

Fig.5 shows the skin elastic modulus and foam shear modulus obtained from experimental flexural tests of the three sandwiches. The values were obtained by applying Eq. 1, 2 and 3 and testing the samples with spans 1000 mm (midspan loading) and 400 mm (quarter point loading). The experimental values are in accordance with datasheet values of constituent materials, and the reported data indicate that skin elastic modulus and shear modulus are lightly affected by manufacturing process.

Fig.5 Summary of the average skin elastic modulus and foam shear modulus of the three sandwich.

Fig. 6 shows the shear strength values obtained from experimental flexural tests of the three sandwiches. These values were obtained with midspan loading (span 400) and quarter point loading (span 600). In fig.7 a photo of broken sample is reported, in which the typical 45° surface fracture for shear rupture can be seen. The crack started under the point in which load was applied, and then propagated in the core, causing a debonding of skins.

Fig.6 Summary of the average shear strengths of the three sandwich for midspan loading (span 400) and quarter point loading (span 600).

Fig.7: photo of a broken sample.

The reported data indicate that shear strength values are lightly affected by manufacturing process as well: going into details, shear strength values are lightly higher for sandwich C, processed with compression moulding technique. Moreover in this case experimental values are lower than datasheet values. The reason is stress concentrations generated by steel bars, even if rubber pads were used with the aim to decrease stress concentrations due to the steel-composite contact. These stress concentrations were evaluated by means of FEM analysis, whose details were reported previously. Fig. 8 shows a comparison between the stress concentrations generated with and without rubber pads, with both midspan loading and quarter point loading. As fig. 8 shows, the use of rubber pads causes a significant decrease of stress concentrations, especially for midspan loading.

3.2 Interfacial fracture tests

In Fig.9 the interfacial fracture energies for the three sandwiches are reported. The experimental data indicate that the fracture energies are higher for sandwiches A and C, averaging between 100 and a110 J/m^2 . Instead sandwich B is characterised by a lower value of G_C , around 30 J/m^2 . This result indicates that the influence of adhesive film is surprisingly negative for sandwiches realised by vacuum bag technique: probably the film obstructed the flow of the polypropylene matrix of the skins within the foam cells, decreasing the skin-core efficiency. This result was not visible during flexural experimental tests, since in that case shear stress caused failure within the core.

Fig. 10 shows the variation of K_I/K_{II} as a function of the crack length, as evaluated by means of FEM analysis, whose details were reported previously. The data indicate that this test is mode I dominated, thus confirming the model used to simulate fracture along skin-core interface. However the agreement between experimental and numerical data for the prevision of the load-displacement curve of the interfacial tests was not good, since in these tests a non-stable fracture propagation was observed (see Fig. 11).

Fig. 8: shear stress distribution in the core for midspan loading (a), midspan loading and rubber pads (b), quarter point loading (c) and quarter point loading and rubber pads.

Fig. 9: summary of the average interfacial fracture energies of the three sandwiches.

Fig. 10: variation of K_I/K_{II} as a function of the crack length as evaluated by means of FEM analysis.

Fig.11: load-displacements curve of an interfacial fracture test on sandwich A.

CONCLUSIONS

A new thermoplastic sandwich, realised with Twintex skins and PET foam core, processed by means of vacuum bag and compression moulding techniques, was characterised by means of flexural and interfacial fracture tests. In addition a low-melting polyester based film was used with the aim to increase the skin-core efficiency of sandwiches realised by vacuum bag technique. Mechanical properties as evaluated from midspan loading and quarter point loading flexural tests showed no dependence on both manufacturing process and low-melting film use. Instead interfacial fracture tests indicated that the influence of adhesive film was negative for sandwiches realised by vacuum bag technique.

The experimental results were better understood thanks to FEM analysis, which also provided useful information for the execution of the tests This approach will be followed for other experimental tests on sandwiches, such as for the evaluation of flat tensile strength and compressive strength.

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